

METHOD OF DEVELOPING TECHNICAL AND TACTICAL TRAINING OF VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS USING PHYSICAL EDUCATION TOOLS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7677482>

Abstract. *The conditions of the volleyball player and the movement on the field, the passing of the ball and the hitting technique were selected based on the exercises adapted to the formation.*

Keywords: *physical preparation, physical condition, exercise, movement, skill, technique, tactics, physical qualities.*

INTRODUCTION. The rich national traditions of the Uzbek people are diverse both in terms of content and form. Among them, the traditions that call for spiritual and physical perfection also have their place. Studying their scientific-pedagogical foundations, analyzing best practices, and rationally using them today serve to enrich the national foundations of physical education classes. Therefore, popularize the traditions.

The development of pedagogical aspects of the use of national traditions in the practical preparation of students for the profession in physical education classes requires solving the following tasks.

1. To study the use of national traditions in physical education lessons (physical exercises in history) and to analyze it scientifically.
2. To determine the perceptions of young people and students about national traditions.
3. Development and implementation of a pedagogical system for the use of national traditions based on research results.

Physical qualities such as being strong and resilient are emphasized in the physical education lessons in the form of symbolic and real heroes such as Alpomish, Barchinoy, To'maris, Jaloliddin Manguberdi. Also, relevant information is given about qualities such as courage, bravery, loyalty to the country.

In practical training (athletics, football, basketball, volleyball, tennis, etc.), in addition to achieving sports skills, they instill the most glorious and highly responsible educational processes of spreading the fame of our Motherland to the world through sports. is going

Therefore, on the basis of our national traditions, not only spiritual-educational, cultural, but also physical maturity is a priority, it has its meaning and expression in life.

Result: The essence, content and characteristics of technical training in the training of young volleyball players are mainly.

Technical training is a long-term specialized pedagogical process, a type of training aimed at mastering the technique of game skills that decide the fate of the competition and its formation. At the initial stage of training, the organization of technical training is of central importance. The effective formation of indicators of technical training depends on the correct use of preparation, approach, special and game exercises.

Technical training in volleyball includes teaching the skills of movement related to attack and defense techniques performed during the game and the processes of gradually forming these

skills. When teaching offensive and defensive techniques, first of all, volleyball player situations and moving around the field, then passing - receiving, passing - receiving, hitting and blocking skills are important. turned Positions and movements are as follows: the position when passing the ball: hips, knees, torso, shoulders, hands - the position of the fingers. Situations when entering the ball, hitting, blocking.

Movements on the field are different and are performed in different directions.

For example, walking to the right, left, forward, backward, running, moving, walking, jumping, sliding. These movement skills are first learned separately, and then they are performed in addition to game skills.

To date, the essence, content and characteristics of the technical training process in the training of young volleyball players have been expressed and covered in detail only in scientific and methodological literature.

Organization of the initial training process of young volleyball players and, in particular, the formation of their technical skills at the initial training stage, requires the determination of selection events, the formation of groups and the rules of training.

Effectiveness of using motion games in formation of ball passing technique. It has been proven in scientific literature that the formation of technical skills in the process of teaching sports techniques depends on the use of customized action games. According to some researchers, active games create an opportunity to form not only physical qualities, but such games can also effectively develop qualities such as precise aiming, precise movement and attention.

Leading volleyball specialists-scientists have proven that the use of action games close to the movement of these technical skills in teaching volleyball techniques gives positive results.

The results obtained in our research also proved that the opinions of the experts mentioned above are objective. Thus, the table shows the results of this study. As can be seen from the table, before the experiment, in the control round, from 3 meters to a 4 m high (on the wall) circular target with a diameter of 30 cm, it was equal to 5.2 times.

It was noted that the performance of young volleyball players in the experimental group was almost at the same level.

Transmission technique was 3.2 in the control group and 3.4 in the research group. So, before the start of the research, the technical training of the children was almost the same.

A 6-month pedagogical experiment was conducted - that is, during this period, the control group was engaged in training with traditional content, while the research group was engaged in exercises that formed the technique of passing the ball and hitting. played games regularly.

Level of formation of ball passing technique in control and research groups.

Control group – n = 12

Research group - n = 12

Groups	From 3 m to a circular target located at a height of 4 m 10 passes		Pass the ball to the basket 10 times from the basketball penalty line	
	Number	Technique	Number	Technique

Control	<u>5,2</u> 6,3	<u>3,2</u> 3,3	<u>4,4</u> 5,2	<u>3,4</u> 3,5
Control	<u>5,3</u> 7,2	<u>3,4</u> 4,4	<u>4,6</u> 7,0	<u>3,3</u> 4,2

It was noted that the results of this pedagogical experiment had a positive effect on the accuracy of passing the ball and its technique. For example, the accuracy of passing the ball in the control group was equal to 5.2 times before the experiment, while the technique was rated as 3.2, after the end of the experiment, these indicators were 6.3 times, and the technique deserves a grade of 3.3.

In the experimental group, the accuracy of passing the ball and its technique were equal to 5.3 times and 3.4 times, respectively, before the experiment. It was noted that the technique increased to 4.4 grades.

The accuracy and technique of passing the ball to the basket or its square target on the board 10 times while standing on the basketball penalty line was 4.4 times and 3.4 in the control group. After the trial period, these indicators did not change much and deserved a rating of 5.2 times and 3.4. It seems that there was no change in the technique of passing the ball.

The indicators recorded in the experimental group were significantly improved. It was noticed that he passed the ball to the basket or the square 7 times, and his technique was rated as 4.2.

The 8-month pedagogical experiment shows that the first task set for the final qualification work was successfully solved and proved that the adapted motion games had a positive effect on the accuracy of passing the ball and its technique. So, there is a reason to say that the effectiveness of forming technical training during training sessions is directly related to action games.

Effectiveness of using action games in the formation of hitting technique. Although the technique of jumping over the net in volleyball is part of medium-complex movement skills, the implementation of this skill in the youngest volleyball children from the initial training stage is recognized by all experts.

According to scientists, for example, correct hitting of a ball passed from 3 zones to 4 zones can be different for volleyball players of different training and age. They recommend using their test exercises in this regard. For example, if 11-year-old children pass the ball passed to 4 zones over the net with 3 shots out of 10 chances, they get a score of "5", 2 shots - a score of "4", 1 shot - a score of "3" and 0 - "2". " rating, 12-year-old children rated 4 strokes as "5", 3 as "4", 2 as "3", and 1 as "2".

We used these test exercises in our research. The table shows the results of the impact test in the control and experimental groups.

According to the results of the research conducted before the experiment, it can be seen that the number of indicators of striking both in the control group and in the experimental group did not differ from the indicators of the above-mentioned authors.

If we observe that the number of strikes in the control group was estimated as 2.4, and the technique as 3.2, these indicators were also estimated as 2.5 and 3.0 in the experimental group.

So, the difference between the two is almost not big, but the impact technique was evaluated with a lower number in the children of the experimental group. However, the results obtained at the end of the pedagogical experiment clearly clarified the issue and demonstrated how effectively the use of specialized movements during training can form the impact technique.

Effectiveness of formation of hitting technique using action games in control and experimental groups.

Control group – n-12

Experimental group - n-12

Groups	Hitting 10 chances	
	Number	Technique
Control	2,4	3,2
	3,2	3,6
Experience	2,5	3,0
	4,8	5,8

For example, if in the control group the number of blows and its technique were rated as 3.2 times and 3.6 respectively, then in the experimental group these indicators were rated as 4.8 and 5.8 after the experiment. . Consequently, during the pedagogical experiment, it was proven that the action games used in training had a positive effect on the number and technique of hitting. So, in the training of young volleyball players and in particular, in the formation of sports skills, the selection of specially specialized action games and their support during the training process allow for the effective formation of these processes.

CONCLUSIONS

1. It became clear from the scientific and methodical literature analyzed in the framework of the topic that the practical importance of specially specialized movement games in training young volleyball players, including in the formation of their technical skills, is incomparable.

2. According to the results of the questionnaire aimed at determining the effectiveness and importance of mobile games in the development of technical training of volleyball players, most of the respondents - coaches could not correctly assess the positive value of mobile games in the process of technical training. Therefore, it was observed that it is not appropriate to use mobile games in their professional activities, and this issue is not emphasized enough.

3. During the research, it was noticed that the children who participated did not meet the requirement of technical training.

4. The results of the pedagogical experiment proved the effectiveness of specially specialized action games in the formation of technical training of young volleyball players and demonstrated how quickly the accuracy of passing and hitting and technique can be formed in a short period of time (6 months).

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